

Understanding Fermat's Last Theorem through Matrix-Graph Relation

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Abstract

Fermat's Last Theorem could be understood by ordinality that matrix provides in node-to-node relation in graph.

1 Introduction

Fermat's Last Theorem was proved by Sir Andrew Wiles in 1994 [1]. The method was to be in an area of utilizing modularity. Although that proof has no doubt to be right, this paper aims to introduce another approach of understanding Fermat's Last Theorem.

2 Decomposing Statement to Matrix

Fermat's Last Theorem states like following:

For any integer $n > 2$, the equation $a^n + b^n = c^n$ has no positive integer solutions.

Figure 1: Default equation of Fermat's Last Theorem

And speaking of matrix, this could be expressed like this:

$$((1 \times p) \cdot (p \times 1))^n + ((1 \times q) \cdot (q \times 1))^n = ((1 \times r) \cdot (r \times 1))^n$$

By conversion to graph, from Figure 2 relation could be expressed in this figure by assuming $a = a_1 \cdot i_1 + a_2 \cdot i_2 + \dots + a_p \cdot i_p$, $b = b_1 \cdot j_1 + b_2 \cdot j_2 + \dots + b_q \cdot j_q$, $c = c_1 \cdot k_1 + c_2 \cdot k_2 + \dots + c_r \cdot k_r$ ($a_x, b_x, c_x \in \mathbf{N}^+$):

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Figure 2: Fermat's Last Theorem to Graph by Node of Natural Number

And by taking maximal p, q combination between vertexes and structuring the vertexes as unit vector in numerical plane, Euclidean norm could be derived :

$$\left\| \left(\sum_{\max p} \vec{n} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{\max q} \vec{n} \right) \right\| = r \Rightarrow n^{(\max p) + (\max q)} = r^n \quad (n \in \mathbf{N}^+) \Rightarrow n = 1 \text{ or } 2$$

References

- [1] A. Wiles, "Modular elliptic curves and Fermat's last theorem," *Annals of mathematics*, vol. 141, no. 3, pp. 443-551, 1995, publisher: JSTOR.